

Invest in Open Infrastructure Summer Business Fellows: A Collaboration with Harvard Business School

Proposal for Alfred P. Sloan Foundation

Kaitlin Thaney (Executive Director, Invest in Open Infrastructure) | December 7, 2020

High-level:

Invest in Open Infrastructure (IOI) was launched to help institutions and funders better invest in the open technology and systems that research and scholarship rely on. We work in concert with institutional leaders, decision makers, and philanthropic funders to better understand the decision points, funding and governance models available, and costs associated with maintaining, sustaining, and scaling open infrastructure projects. Our aim is to shed light on the current funding landscape and provide trusted recommendations, tools, and investment strategies to foster a more sustainable open infrastructure ecosystem.

IOI's work is centered around providing targeted, evidence-based guidance and support to institutions and funders of open infrastructure to help them become wiser about where to invest.

The work outlined below represents an opportunity to build our capacity for economic analysis, modeling, and research by collaborating with the Harvard Business School community via (2) paid student internships. The research questions further explore areas of interest surfaced through our [Future of Open Scholarship project](#)¹ by institutional leaders and research organizations to assist in their decision making and analysis, and build on modeling work we're currently undertaking with Kate Pugh of AlignConsulting and Columbia University.

Proposed research questions - and why they're important

The questions below are designed to expand our understanding of the costs associated and economics of ongoing maintenance and sustainability of open infrastructure in research and higher education. They build on [findings surfaced in our Future of Open Scholarship research](#)², a six-month project with 100+ decision makers from institutions and supporting research and scholarship organizations, outlining their needs, constraints, opportunities for collective action, and first cuts at costs and benefits models to bolster institutional decision making (in particular to argue for more investment in shared infrastructure).

That work has provided us with a strong base to build from and has directly engaged members of the research community, budget holders, and infrastructure providers in discussing models for collective funding, shared services, and risk. While we are writing up that research now, we also

¹ <https://investinopen.org/research/future-of-open-scholarship/>

² https://docs.google.com/presentation/d/1plh8SzzdWGStXmsr_WtZbZh4B0uU7nnQPgf8x7zU-4Q/edit

have outlined additional questions that have arisen from that work, for which we'd welcome expertise from the Harvard Business School student body to further investigate.

As that research is actively being synthesized and written up, we have outlined a few areas of exploration to be further honed in Phase I of this work (as outlined under the Work Plan) with collaborators like Frank Nagle at HBS in early 2021.

They include:

- **Costs of system interoperability:**
 - What costs are associated with building interoperability among existing open source systems utilized in higher education (e.g. content and data repositories)?
 - What costs and benefits are associated with crafting, adopting, and employing open standards to facilitate system interoperability?
- **Economics of distributed infrastructure (development & governance):**
 - What are the economic factors associated with decentralized, community-governed infrastructure for research?
 - What examples or supporting models exist to help calculate the return on investment of distributed governance, participation, and maintenance?
 - What are the “hidden” or “invisible” costs associated with open, distributed infrastructure? (e.g. direct vs indirect costs, staffing and governance, ongoing maintenance)
- **Exploring collective funding and service models:**
 - What efficiencies exist at the various network layers (consortias, regional organizations, national funding programmes, etc) when it comes to shared infrastructure costs?
 - What does risk look like across various collective funding models, and how best to mitigate? (e.g. membership models, national funded infrastructure, cooperatives)
 - What sorts of shared infrastructure make sense for collective, cross-institutional levels of support?

Current state of research

Our work is informed and shaped by research done to examine the challenges and opportunity costs of digital public infrastructure (outside of the research sector) and open source software development, more broadly. That includes Nadia Egbhal's report "[Roads and Bridges: The Unseen Labor Behind our Digital Infrastructure](https://www.fordfoundation.org/work/learning/research-reports/roads-and-bridges-the-unseen-labor-behind-our-digital-infrastructure/)"³ and her recent book, "[Working in Public: The Making and Maintenance of Open Source Software](https://www.amazon.com/Working-Public-Making-Maintenance-Software/dp/0578675862)"⁴.

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<https://www.fordfoundation.org/work/learning/research-reports/roads-and-bridges-the-unseen-labor-behind-our-digital-infrastructure/>

⁴ <https://www.amazon.com/Working-Public-Making-Maintenance-Software/dp/0578675862>

Our work is also influenced by the research of Frank Nagle, an assistant professor in the Strategy Unit at Harvard Business School, and Shane Greenstein, a professor at Harvard Business School, co-director of the HBS Digital Initiative, and co-director of the program on the economics of digitization at the National Bureau of Economic Research. Together, their work explores the economics of IT, Internet infrastructure collaboration, and crowdsourcing, specializing in that of the open source software movement. Their 2013 working paper in the National Bureau of Economic Research on “[Digital Dark Matter](#)⁵” in particular sought to assess the rate of return on open source software solutions like Apache and to quantify the value of technology and commerce built on top of open solutions. We aim with this effort (and our research more broadly, moving forward) to explore ways to further incorporate this level of economic thinking about value adds, associated and hidden costs, and rates of return to the open research infrastructure field. In our research to date, information about the costs for open research infrastructure development, adoption, and maintenance are difficult to come by, often contributing to challenges at the institutional level in making a more robust investment case for better resourcing for critical open infrastructure relied on by an institution.

The work of the (2) summer fellows through this paid internship will help address this gap in providing dedicated expertise from the HBS student body on some of the challenges and questions we’re grappling with as a community.

Why is the proposer qualified to address the research question for which funds are being sought?

Kaitlin Thaney is the Executive Director of Invest in Open Infrastructure, a non-profit initiative designed to enable durable, scalable, and long lasting open scientific and scholarly infrastructure to emerge, thrive, and deliver its benefits on a global scale. Her career has been dedicated to building, enabling, scaling, and sustaining research infrastructure, both for- and non-profit, and her current work is dedicated to shedding light on the costs, models, and strategies needed to improve the sustainability of open technology in research.

She previously served as the Endowment Director for the Wikimedia Foundation, where she led development of a fund to sustain the future of Wikipedia and free knowledge. Prior to joining Wikimedia, Thaney directed the program portfolio for the Mozilla Foundation, following her time building the Mozilla Science Lab, a program to serve the open research community. She was on the founding team for Digital Science, where she helped launch and advise programs to serve researchers worldwide, building on her time at Creative Commons, where she crafted legal, technical, and social infrastructure for sharing data on the web.

Research methodology (summary)

Our work is anchored in a human-centered design approach. We draw from the best of field research, market research, and participatory action research.

These approaches tackle interactive systems development (both technical and social) by aiming to make systems usable and useful by focusing on the users, their needs and requirements, and

⁵ <https://www.nber.org/papers/w19507>

utilizing various methods of iterative design to outline shared solutions and opportunities for collective action. Building on participatory action research, our approach intentionally focuses on moving towards producing solutions (in our case action plans, testing new business models, models to support decision making, and working to establish trust and support among cohorts to empower them to move towards adoption).

For these (2) paid-student-internships, we will work with the selected fellows to scope their 8-week research projects to build off of our existing models, data collected, and field research to provide a base for the students to work from. This includes over 75 hours of user interviews with institutional leaders about their needs, usage, and perceived risks for open infrastructure for the Future of Open Scholarship project, as well as additional data analysis work looking at available funding data from key philanthropies.

We also intend to explore areas of commonality and shared interest with Frank Nagle, an assistant professor in the Strategy Unit at Harvard Business School, who has expressed his support and interest in collaborating on this effort to build a bridge with the Harvard Business School research community. For more information on our research methods, please see the Empirical Research Methods section in the Appendices.

Work plan

We have outlined the following (3) phases of this project, with the fellows beginning their work with us after their term concludes in May 2021 for 8-weeks. We anticipate the work in February to May to be led by IOI ED Kaitlin Thaney, with additional consultation and support of Frank Nagle at HBS in helping us circulate the role with the HBS community.

Timeline & key milestones:

- **Phase I: Preparation for fellows:**
 - Refining & posting fellowship job post (January - February 2021)
 - Fellows search & recruitment (March - May 2021)
- **Phase II: Summer internships:**
 - **Anticipated start:** June 8, 2021
 - Fellow onboarding (June 8-12)
 - Outline project plans (June 19)
 - Mid-way share out on IOI Community Call (July 10)
 - *Weekly project check-ins*
 - Project wrap-up (July 27-31)
 - **Anticipated end date:** July 31, 2021
- **Phase III: Reporting & program evaluation:** Aug - Sept 2021
 - IOI ED will issue a program evaluation / participant survey to fellows and stakeholders
 - IOI ED will work with Fellows to write up final deliverables (e.g. blog posts, working papers, resources to post on the website)

Anticipated project outputs

We anticipate this work to lead to the production of blog posts to share out research progress, working papers/preprints (where appropriate), and supporting models and/or frameworks to supplement analysis based on the research questions above. We also anticipate Fellows to share their work on IOI Monthly Community Calls throughout their internship.

Fellows' work will be made openly available under a CC-BY-4.0 license, and be made available on our website at investinopen.org. We will also explore venues to share this work that align with our values to provide openly available and accessible research, including but not limited to open repositories and preprint services such as Zenodo, DASH (Harvard's Open Access repository), and the Nationale Bureau of Economic Research.

Budget summary

The costs outlined in the prepared budget namely support stipends for (2) Harvard Business School students, at the rate of \$1300 a week*, for 8 weeks. (**This figure is the baseline level of support for paid internships without triggering the need for Harvard-provided financial aid to offset student costs*).

In addition to the fellows stipends, we have budgeted for 20% of IOI Executive Director Kaitlin Thaney's time for 12-weeks, to provide support both before and after the fellowships. (Work prior to the start of the fellowship may be spread out over a series of months, to allow the internship to be posted along Harvard's suggested timeline, interviews and recruitment of summer fellows, and time following their internships to write up findings and share a project evaluation survey with participants and key stakeholders.

Lastly, we have budgeted for secretarial and clerical services, which include financial administration, strategic, and administrative support, and will be provided by Code for Science & Society and the San Souci Group.

Other sources of research support

IOI is supported through a mix of philanthropic support and financial commitments from institutions and consortia-based organizations. Our diverse network of partners — many of whom have made a financial commitment to IOI in the midst of a global pandemic — underscores the critical nature of this work for academic institutions and the sector. We believe this signals a willingness to engage with IOI over the long term.

Our current funding is allocated to IOI core staff (Kaitlin Thaney) and short term contractors for additional support for project-based work, modeling, and data analysis. We also have dedicated support for the Joint Roadmap for Open Science Tools (JROST) conference, including support for a Rapid Response Fund we're piloting for the event to support the open infrastructure community. We have noted those support levels in the list below as "JROST-pending".

For FY21-22, we have operational reserves from Schmidt Futures, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, and the Libraries of the Big Ten Alliance that will ensure continuity of core staff (Thaney) through March 2022. A full list of our support to date is noted below.

We are seeking support to further scale our operations to build in more dedicated data analyst capacity as the need and demand for our work grows in 2021, and are in active conversations with the Mellon Foundation, Arcadia Fund, and EBSCO about support to facilitate that growth. This support would also directly assist with that.

As a sustainability focused non-profit initiative, we are keenly aware of the strains that exist on the current funding landscape for open infrastructure non-profits. We are dedicated at IOI to exploring revenue models that both align with a values-base that employs trust with our partners and is centered on transparency, openness and clear value-add — and that’s reflected in the institutional funding we’ve garnered in the past few months to directly support decision makers and administrators. We continue to explore business models that both diversify our support levels and work with institutions, government funders, philanthropic entities and others to ensure our offerings are best addressing unmet needs to improve funding and resourcing for open infrastructure in research and education.

Center for Research Libraries	\$5,000
Stanford University	\$5,000
Iowa State University	\$5,000
North Carolina State University	\$10,000
Indiana University - Bloomington	\$10,000
SPARC	\$20,000
SUNY Buffalo	\$20,000
Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (JROST)	\$50,000
Chan Zuckerberg Initiative (IOI operations)	\$80,000
Sloan Foundation (IOI)	\$50,000
Schmidt Futures (initial grant)	\$150,000
Schmidt Futures (matching grant)	\$150,000
Libraries of the Big Ten Alliance	\$20,000
Wellcome Trust	\$40,000
Next Generation Library Publishing - Assessment Pilot (Educopia; Arcadia Fund)	\$20,000
ITHAKA (JROST-pending)	\$11,500
CrossRef (JROST-pending)	\$2,300

Hypothesis (JROST-pending)	\$1,000
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Status of current and/or previous Sloan grants

We are fortunate to have \$50,000 USD from the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation to support our first year of operations. The grant (#G-2019-12547), initially issued in November 2019 has an end date of March 30, 2021, and is currently being utilized to support our work in establishing a network aimed at integrating and expanding open infrastructure initiatives.